

Status of the MUonE experiment and preliminary results from the 2025 run

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Abstract

The MUonE experiment at CERN aims to provide an independent measurement of the leading-order hadronic contribution to the muon $g-2$ (a_μ^{HVP}), complementary to the existing ones. The innovative approach proposed by MUonE is based on the measurement of the hadronic contribution to the running of the QED coupling, which can be extracted from a precise measurement of the shape of the differential cross section of the $\mu-e$ elastic scattering. The experiment is carried out at the M2 beam line at CERN, where a 160 GeV muon beam is scattered off the atomic electrons of a low- Z target. The M2 beam line provides the necessary intensity needed to reach the statistical goal in few years of data taking. The experimental challenge is the precise control of the systematic effects. A first run with a minimal prototype detector was performed in 2023, while a pilot run including a reduced setup of the full detector components was carried out in Summer 2025. The status of the experiment will be presented, along with first preliminary results from the 2025 run and the future plans.

1 Introduction

The muon anomaly (a_μ) is a low energy observable that has been both measured and computed with very high precision over the last decades, providing a stringent test of the Standard Model. In June 2025, the Muon $g-2$ Collaboration at Fermilab released its final measurement of a_μ , achieving an impressive precision of 127 ppb [1]. The result is in agreement with previous measurements performed at Fermilab and BNL [2–4]. In the next years, a new experiment at J-PARC will provide a further cross-check by measuring a_μ with a completely different technique [5]. On the theory side, the limiting factor on the Standard Model prediction of a_μ is the evaluation of the leading order hadronic vacuum polarization term, a_μ^{HVP} . At present, a_μ^{HVP} is either determined from lattice QCD calculations, or through a dispersion integral over the cross section $e^+e^- \rightarrow \text{hadrons}$. While the lattice QCD result is currently in agreement with the experimental value, there are $2-5\sigma$ tensions among different datasets used as input to the dispersion integral [6]. This unclear situation prevents a firm comparison between theory and experiment.

2 The MUonE experiment

The MUonE Collaboration aims at providing an independent evaluation of a_μ^{HVP} through an innovative approach, based on the extraction of the hadronic component to the running of the QED coupling ($\Delta\alpha_{\text{had}}$) from the shape of the $\mu-e$ elastic scattering differential cross section [7–10].

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Figure 1: Schematic view of the MUonE experimental apparatus (not to scale).

The experiment is carried out at the M2 beam line at CERN SPS, where a 160 GeV muon beam is scattered off the electrons of a low-Z target. The direction of the interaction products is detected by a 1 m long tracking station equipped with silicon strip sensors. The scattering angles of the outgoing muon and electron produced in elastic interactions are correlated by kinematics, providing an effective tool to reject background events. The primary background process is expected to be e^+e^- pair production by muons interacting with the target nuclei, if one of the three outgoing particles escapes the detector acceptance. The final detector, sketched in Figure 1, will be a repetition of 40 stations, each equipped with a target and acting as an independent unit. In this way, the muon beam will be re-used, keeping the target thickness $\lesssim 2$ cm without affecting the collected statistics. This is essential for preserving the μ - e elastic correlation, which would otherwise be degraded by multiple scattering effects in the target. The apparatus is completed by an electromagnetic calorimeter and a muon ID system placed after the tracking stations. They will provide particle identification and a measurement of the electron energy. A beam momentum spectrometer (BMS) will allow a precise measurement of the muon beam momentum. The main challenge of the experiment is to keep the systematic error on the shape of the differential cross section at the level of 10 ppm. This will allow a sub-percent determination of a_μ^{HVP} , making the measurement by MUonE competitive with the current evaluations. This goal requires to compute the higher order corrections to the elastic scattering at least up to NNLO [10, 11]. Two independent Monte Carlo codes have been developed for this purpose [12, 13]. Additionally, dedicated generators have been developed to model the main background processes [14, 15]. On the experimental side, the average beam energy must be known at the level of a few MeV, the longitudinal position of the tracking sensors must be stable $< 10 \mu\text{m}$ within a station, and a high uniformity of the tracking performance and detector resolution is required [10].

3 The 2025 Run: MUonE Phase 1

In Summer 2025, MUonE carried out a run with a small scale version of the final apparatus, composed of three tracking stations, a prototype calorimeter, an additional tracking station placed downstream of the calorimeter acting as muon ID, two plastic scintillators placed before and after the three tracking stations used as timing detectors, and the BMS, whose current implementation consisted of two tracking stations placed before and after the 16 T · m bending magnet located on the beam line upstream of the MUonE detector. The second and third tracking stations were equipped with a graphite target 2 cm thick, whilst the first station was employed to detect the incoming muons. Figure 2 shows the layout of a tracking station. The mechanical support is made of Invar, a Fe-Ni alloy with a coefficient of thermal expansion ~ 1 ppm/K, which, combined with a temperature-controlled environment stable to 1 °C, ensures the required 10 μm longitudinal stability. Each tracking station is equipped with six 2S modules,

Figure 2: Schematic of a MUonE tracking station.

silicon strip sensors in production for the CMS Phase-2 upgrade [16]. Each module is composed of two closely spaced sensors with a sensitive area of $\sim 10 \times 10 \text{ cm}^2$ and a strip pitch of $90 \mu\text{m}$. The two sensors measure the same coordinate and are read out by the same electronics. The 40 MHz read-out rate is capable of sustaining the $\sim 50 \text{ MHz}$ maximum beam in-spill rate. The modules are arranged in three pairs. The first and third ones measure the horizontal and vertical directions (XY), while the second pair is rotated by 45° to solve reconstruction ambiguities (UV). XY modules are also tilted by 233 mrad around their strip axis, increasing the effective strip density and thereby improving the hit resolution. This has been verified by reconstructing a clean sample of single non-interacting muons passing through the apparatus. Figure 3 shows the unbiased residuals of two contiguous tilted and non-tilted modules. The standard deviation of the tilted module residuals is a factor of 2 smaller than the non-tilted one, demonstrating a significant resolution improvement due to the tilted assembly. Work is in progress for a precise evaluation of the hit resolution and the assessment of residual systematic errors in the analysis.

Figure 3: Left (right): unbiased residuals for a non-tilted (tilted) module, computed as the difference between the track position extrapolated to the module (x_{Track}) and the hit position (x_{Hit}).

Differently from the three main tracking stations, the muon ID is equipped with two non-tilted XY pairs of 2S modules. The same applies for the two BMS stations, albeit the modules are mounted on a carbon fibre mechanical support. The prototype calorimeter is a 5×5 matrix of PbWO_4 crystals, borrowed from the CMS ECAL. Each crystal has $2.85 \times 2.85 \times 23 \text{ cm}^3$ dimensions ($25X_0$), and is read out by a $10 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$ APD coupled to MGPA preamplifiers [17].

All the sub-detectors are read out by the Serenity board, developed for the CMS Phase-2 upgrade [18]. Since the M2 muon beam is asynchronous with respect to the DAQ clock, the system operates without a trigger, meaning that data from all the sub-detectors are continuously processed at a 40 MHz rate. A two-stage DAQ design has been implemented in the 2025 run. Firstly, data is aggregated per sub-detector, and an online event filter based on the occupancy in the three tracking stations is applied to select only events of interest for the offline analysis. This allowed to reduce the data written to disk by a factor ~ 100 compared to previous MUonE runs, where the entire 40 MHz stream was saved. In the second stage, an event builder groups data from the different sub-detectors in time-consistent packets, which are then transferred to disk.

3.1 Elastic events reconstruction with ECAL and muon ID

The basic signature of a $\mu - e$ elastic event is a pair of tracks reconstructed in the station downstream of a target associated in a vertex with a track detected in the upstream station, representing the incoming muon. Due to momentum conservation, the three tracks lie on the same plane, whereas this is not true for background events. The planarity of the reconstructed event therefore provides an effective variable to select elastic events, along with the requirement that the vertex lies inside the target. This selection is applied to a subsample of candidate elastic events as shown in Figure 4-left. Given the kinematic correlation between muon and electron, there is an ambiguity region when both scattering angles are $< 5 \text{ mrad}$, if only the tracker information is used in the analysis. For this reason, the two angles are labeled according to their magnitude. The ambiguity can be resolved taking advantage of the ECAL or the muon

ID. The two outgoing tracks are extrapolated to the muon ID using a Kalman filter, and the track matching at least three hits in three different muon ID modules is tagged as the muon. The other track is required not to match any hit to be labeled as the electron. This allows to populate the ambiguity region, as shown in Figure 4-right. The band of events visible along the horizontal axis is mainly due to large angle electrons entering the detector acceptance due to multiple scattering effects, and can be removed by requiring $\theta_\mu > 0.2$ mrad.

Figure 4: Scattering angles distribution of elastic candidates with tracker selection only (left) and after the muon ID particle identification (right). The red line represents the expected elasticity curve for a 160 GeV muon beam. The green dashed line corresponds to equal scattering angles. The region above the green line is populated after applying the muon ID selection.

On the other hand, a minimum energy deposit in the ECAL of 1 GeV can be applied to reject uninteresting low energy events. The ECAL cluster centroid can be then exploited to match the extrapolated position of the candidate electron track, and the cluster energy is required to follow the kinematic correlation between the electron energy and its scattering angle. Figure 5 shows a different subsample before and after applying the ECAL selection to preselected tracker events, demonstrating good capabilities of selecting elastic interactions. Work is in progress to combine both ECAL and muon ID information into a single event selection.

Figure 5: Scattering angles distribution of elastic candidates with tracker selection only (left) and after the ECAL particle identification (right). The red line represents the expected elasticity curve for a 160 GeV muon beam. The green dashed line corresponds to equal scattering angles. The region above the green line is populated after applying the ECAL selection.

4 Conclusions and future plans

MUonE completed a successful run in Summer 2025, collecting more than 5×10^{11} interaction triggers. Ongoing analysis aims to evaluate the detector performance, assess the main systematic errors and provide a proof of principle measurement of the leptonic component to the QED running, $\Delta\alpha_{\text{lep}}$. Results will form the basis for the full-scale experiment proposal, targeting data taking after the CERN Long Shutdown 3.

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